

No one is left behind: how Sogrape promotes sustainable viticulture in Portugal's Douro Valley

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Keywords: Copper; Douro; Plant protection; Sustainability; Viticulture.

Abstract. SOGRAPE, a family-owned wine company, developed a Global Sustainability Approach strongly aligned with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals. Novel plant protection strategies minimizing negative environmental impacts are fundamental for sustainable viticulture. Thus, two projects are underway in SOGRAPE's Quinta do Seixo and Quinta do Sairrão, two properties located in Cima Corgo sub-region of Douro valley. Douro viticulture has unique microclimates, created by a rugged landscape and steep slopes. Vineyards with different topography, altitude and slope aspect are used for these projects. Project NOVATERRA (funded by EU's Horizon 2020) aims to improve sustainability by integrating new plant protection products (PPPs) of natural origin with biodiversity conservation, precision agriculture, robotics, and integrated soil and crop management. The project uses a practical and integrative approach, promoting multivariate case studies, in real scale trials to speed adoption of any successful solutions. Project COPPEREPLACE (funded by EU's Interreg Sudoe) aims to reduce copper use in vineyards. Excessive exposure to copper accumulation in the soil harms the environment and human health. The project trials strategies to reduce the use of copper in vineyards with alternative PPPs, while evaluating strategies to remediate copper-contaminated soils. All SOGRAPE vineyards are certified sustainable (Integrated Production) and have automated weather stations providing data to support decision-making in disease risk management while reducing environmental impact. Novel techniques gauged in these two projects work for the same goal of paving the way towards increasingly sustainable agriculture, combined into an integrated vine protection strategy. Results will be widely disseminated in open events and communications as well as through national and international networks, fulfilling SOGRAPE's pledge to contribute for knowledge dissemination among its grape suppliers.

Introduction

The family-owned wine company, SOGRAPE, created a Global Sustainability Approach program, which aims to be a catalyst for positive societal change, while respecting the limits of the planet and paving the way to a healthier planet. As a wine company with social responsibility, SOGRAPE operates and invests smartly to reduce its environmental footprint, implementing initiatives that have positive impacts on biodiversity.

In this sense, two international projects are underway in SOGRAPE's Quinta do Seixo and Quinta do Sairrão, two properties located in Cima Corgo central sub-region of Douro valley. The Douro Wine Region (DWR) in Portugal is a mountain viticulture region, presenting different

microclimates, due to its rugged orography and steep slopes. The unique particularities of this region are subjects of study in these projects, with the same goal of paving the way for an increasingly more sustainable agriculture.

The NOVATERRA (funded by EU's Horizon 2020 - 101000554) project's overall goal is to ensure food safety and access to a healthy diet for a growing population, without overlooking the guidelines of Directive 2009/128/EC for the sustainable use of pesticides. The project's purpose is to create a more comprehensive approach to the future of the agriculture business, based on case studies with multivariate analysis of the use of biopesticides, optimized smart agriculture techniques, robotics, new soil management strategies and a functional biodiversity assessment.

The COPPEREPLACE project (funded by EU's Interreg Sudoe - SOE4/P1/E1000) purposes to reduce the use of copper in the vineyard. Use of copper has been increasingly limited by regulations due to its potential to harm the environment and human health. The project's overall goal is to test and implement new products and efficient strategies to reduce the use of copper in vineyards. Different alternatives have been implemented to identify vulnerable soils, and assessment strategies for remediation of copper-contaminated soils.

In this context, this paper provides an overview of SOGRAPE's strategies for a more sustainable viticulture.

Methods and sources

In both projects, three methodologies have been implemented in Quinta do Seixo (Figure 2) and Quinta do Sairrão (Figure 3), such as: (1) spraying of new plant protection products (PPP), such as plant resistance elicitors and/or other new products allowing for a lower copper use; (2) site-specific management for spray application of PPP, using the concept of variable rate application (VRA); and (3) soil management, by analysis of soils vulnerability and nonchemical weed control, using mechanical methods. In all methodologies, control plants treated with the usual procedure and untreated plants were included.

Figure 1. Trials experimental design for PPP application. Blue rectangle: small-scale trial. Green rectangle: large-scale trial.

Figure 1 represents the two different trials design approach implemented for new PPP application. In the small-scale trial, randomized blocks design with 4 replicates, 4 plants per each replicate were assessed for each modality/treatment. In the large-scale trial, 3 replicates of 3 rows each were treated with each tested compound. On each replicate, observations were made in 4 blocks with 4 plants each in the middle row only, the adjacent ones serving as buffers between trial

modalities. They were compared to plants treated with the usual protection strategy and also with untreated plants to verify pest pressure.

The methodologies used in both projects propose integrated approaches with the objective of reducing the level of contentious chemicals use, while ensuring an adequate level of protection throughout the season. Both are deployed as real-scale research trials using large vineyard areas and real-life application methods that can be easily adopted by other farmers. Wide dissemination and knowledge networks are planned to boost adoption of any results.

Theoretical framework and operational concepts

Towards more sustainable agriculture, a reduction of contentious pesticides is required. This can be obtained by developing innovative eco-friendly strategies that protect both the environment and human health (Burketova *et al.*, 2015; Héloir *et al.*, 2019). One of these strategies can be using elicitors or resistance inducers that stimulate the plant immune system. Other new technologies, as variable rate technology (VRT) supports vineyard management minimizing spray losses, applying precise amounts according to previously collected data, such as canopy size, season, and growth phase (Hołownicki *et al.*, 2017; Sahu *et al.*, 2019; Abbas *et al.*, 2020). Also, for weed control without spraying herbicides mechanical weeding approaches are hopeful alternatives, promoting soil health and overall biodiversity, while maintaining crop profitability (Van Der Weide *et al.*, 2008; Fountas *et al.*, 2020).

On the other hand, the importance of real-scale investigation has been quite in-depth. Studies have shown that the whole-of-block experimental approach on-farm trials are useful in vineyards and offers both researchers and vineyard managers a means of acquiring more useful information than would be obtained from a conventional plot-based approach (Bramley *et al.*, 2011; Panten *et al.*, 2010). On-Farm Experimentation (OFE) is an innovation process that brings a response to the inability of small-plot trials commonly used in on-farm research to provide sufficiently actionable insights to farmers. This vision is based on six guiding principles, allowing agricultural stakeholders together around mutually beneficial experimentation to support farmers' own management decisions (Lacoste *et al.*, 2021).

Taking all of this into account, the techniques gauged in these two projects work for the same goal of paving the way towards increasingly sustainable agriculture, combined into an integrated vine protection strategy.

Background

All vineyards owned by SOGRAPE are certified sustainable (according to IOBC Integrated Production guidelines for grapes), including, Quinta do Seixo and Quinta do Sairrão, two properties located in Cima Corgo central sub-region of the Douro valley with different orography and microclimates. Automated weather stations in vineyards also provide data to support decision-making in protecting vineyards from disease while reducing environmental impact. Integrated Production in SOGRAPE's vineyards is based on continuous improvement, with the aim of achieving ever more sustainable farming.

Figure 16. Quinta do Seixo location (Coordinates: 41°10'05.3"N 7°33'18.5"W), Valença do Douro, Tabuaço - Portugal.

Figure 3. Quinta do Sairrão location (Coordinates: 41°07'36.10"N 7°24'07.26"W), São João da Pesqueira - Portugal.

Results

In the case of terraced vineyards, due to their rugged orography and steep slopes, the implementation of experimental trials is more complex than in flat vineyards. Slope convexities created by water lines are areas of greater pressure from disease that alternate, in the same row of vines, with concavities. In vertical row vineyards, costs of manual application of PPP increase because of inherent morosity in climbing slopes that may exceed 40%. Considering all these factors for the experimental design, an approach derived from medical epidemiology was applied, using areas for each modality larger than

the observation area (number of observed plants) to simultaneously obtain adequate buffering between adjacent trial modalities and confound a large number of different situations for all modalities to control only the relevant variables, in this case orography, altitude and slope aspect. The research work is still in progress, results and outputs of these two projects are expected in 2023.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this article highlights difficulties of implementing trials in slope vineyards and strategies to solve their inherent variability. The work developed under these two projects, NOVATERRA and COPPEREPLACE, contributes for integrated vine management strategy, paving the way towards increasingly sustainable viticulture.

Acknowledgements: This work is supported by Interreg Sudoe Program (COPPEREPLACE project) with grant agreement number SOE4/P1/E1000 and by European Commission's Horizon 2020 (NOVATERRA project) with grant agreement number 101000554.

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